

DIGITAL BLOCKCHAIN
TECHNOLOGY IN ENERGY:
A TECHNICAL REPORT FOR
SMART TRANSACTIONS IN THE
AGE OF SOCIAL DISTANCING

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Abstract

With the rapid growth of renewable energy resources, energy trading has been shifting from the centralized manner to distributed manner. Blockchain, as a distributed public ledger technology, has been widely adopted in the design of new energy trading schemes. However, there are many challenging issues in blockchain-based energy trading, e.g., low efficiency, high transaction cost, and security and privacy issues. To tackle these challenges, many solutions have been proposed. In this survey, the blockchain-based energy trading in the electrical power system is thoroughly investigated. Firstly, the challenges in blockchain-based energy trading are identified and summarized. Then, the existing energy trading schemes are studied and classified into three categories based on their main focuses: energy transaction, consensus mechanism, and system optimization. Blockchain-based energy trading has been a popular research topic, new blockchain architectures, models and products are continually emerging to overcome the limitations of existing solutions, forming a virtuous circle. The internal combination of different blockchain types and the combination of blockchain with other technologies improve the blockchain-based energy trading system to better satisfy the practical requirements of modern power systems. However, there are still some problems to be solved, for example, the lack of regulatory system, environmental challenges and so on.

Keywords: Blockchain, Electrical power system, Energy trading.

Section 1

1.1 Introduction

Power systems is undergoing a change. Increased reliance on digital transactions and energy trading is current, and expanding across the world. In an age where social distancing due to massively infectious viral pandemics, the digital revolution, requiring minimum physical interaction, may become more than a nice to have but a necessity. Already the introduction of Local Energy Communities (LEC) was touted in Kahn (2020, April 1), in the report “Blockchain in energy : a new paradigm for Local Energy Communities (LEC) of the 4IR”.

A looming energy crisis and environmental pollution have become two critical concerns in the last decade (Lan et al., 2016). The smart grid with renewable energy resources is a promising approach to alleviate these problems, and its implementation can be facilitated by micro grids. In smart grids, new models, technologies, and flexible solutions are to be developed for intelligent energy management, to facilitate the optimal energy and power flow strategies. Specifically, energy trading, as an essential component in energy management, is undergoing an evolution from centralized to distributed manner. In the traditional energy market, the energy users can only buy electricity from the power utilities. In a smart grid, the energy users play a role as both power consumer and supplier. The excessive renewable energy generations can be traded with the utility and other users in the deficit of power supplies for mutual benefits.

The development of the traditional centralized energy market model has experienced and faced many problems:

- Centralized management. In traditional energy market model, energy trading is highly dependent on the centralized third party servers, thus it is apt to cause single point of failures (Ning Wang, Xu, Xu, & Shao, 2018). In addition, the centralized management leads to high operating costs, low transparency, and the potential risk of transaction data tampering.
- Privacy protection and security issues. Third parties may disclose the user’s energy generation pattern and predict a user’s daily activities based on historical data (Costa, Figuerêdo, & Oliveira, 2017). Meanwhile, communication security is also a challenging issue.
- The lack of competition between renewable energy pricing and traditional market pricing will discourage the investment in renewable energy.
- The power grid lacks the resilience to cyber-attacks.
- Electricity comes mainly from large energy plants, which needs to pass through long-distance power transmission line before reaching the end customers. Due to the complexity of the power management, it is difficult to meet the dynamic energy demands timely and flexibly(Gregoratti & Matamoros, 2015).
- Long-distance one-way energy transmission makes the power supply be vulnerable to disruptions. In modern electrical power systems, the distributed bidirectional energy management is desirable to improve the system efficiency and stability(Jogunola et al., 2018).

Issues like efficiency, demand, cost and emissions need to be fully taken into consideration while the transition from traditional power grid to smart grids with LEC's is being done. Renewable energy generation is now becoming common in remote villages and districts (Matasane CM and Kahn MTE, 2019). As the technologies emerge, blockchain has been widely adopted in many fields for its well-known advantages.

Blockchain was indeed flawed when it first emerged. Nevertheless, studies have identified these problems and made corresponding improvements, like the measurement research and exploration of the re-parameterization of blockchain to enhance its scalability namely Bitcoin-NG. Bitcoin-NG is a Byzantine fault tolerant blockchain protocol that is robust to extreme churn and shares the same trust model as Bitcoin.. The technologies used in Blockchain include, Internet of Things (IoT), public social services, financial reputation system, security and privacy, and so on. For example (Zyskind, Nathan, & Pentland, 2015), Blockchain is used to enhance privacy through a decentralized personal information management system. It can make sure that users have control over data, proving that blockchain may function as a crucial tool for trusted computing. The model proposed in (Kosba, Miller, Shi, Wen, & Papamanthou, 2016) , called "Hawk" , also addresses the issue of transaction privacy, by using an intelligent contract system that enables the compiler to automatically generate an efficient encryption protocol. As for the IoT, blockchain can enable the sharing of services and resources, and automate several existing time-consuming workflows in the form of cryptographic authentication. Blockchain can also be employed for secure decentralized energy management. Another study has used blockchain to design privacy-protected search scheme for malicious servers. Moreover, it can even be applied to data sharing schemes to make sure of the fairness of incentives.

The integration of blockchain technology into energy trading may be a novel and promising area of research, and lots of studies have made efforts during this regard. Before formally attempting to mix blockchain with the energy trading model, some researchers first studied the use of distributed systems to the energy market. Proof by facts, Peer-to-Peer (P2P) network model enables the energy market to operate in a consumer-centered manner and support the participation of the so-called "prosumers", which has greatly improved the flexibility of the normal mode of energy market. As shown in (Abdella & Shuaib, 2018), P2P network can create a competitive energy market and increase the overall efficiency of the power market. Additionally, the distributed system can also provide high-precision demand response signals, reduce cost and improve speed. Moreover, it solves the matter of system scalability and mobility, and creates a competitive market that benefits small-scale prosumers.

Additionally, to improve the utilization of renewable energy, an adaptive distributed energy scheduling scheme is proposed to coordinate the microgrids and renewable energy generation. Many studies have shown the benefits of introducing blockchain technology into the energy trading systems. For example, high computing capacity may be realized with blockchain at a marginal cost, and therefore the consensus mechanism can make sure of the optimal solution. In

addition, it can prevent fake transactions and establish an open and transparent system . All nodes can work independently towards system equilibrium without central supervision(Pop et al., 2018).

Currently, blockchain-based energy trading isn't just a theoretical topic, but there are already many practical applications. For instance, Exergy team developed Brooklyn Microgrid in April 2016, which is the world's first practical blockchain-based energy trading platform(Shrestha et al., 2019). In France, there is a project named Sun chain, which uses the Hyper Ledger Fabric platform to create a blockchain virtual network for solar energy prosumers and can efficiently deal with the energy transactions at low cost. Although only a limited number of users are involved in Sunchain project, the use of solar energy in social housing has been realized and therefore the share of electricity generated per unit of housing can be traced. Power Ledgerin Australia (PLA) may be a trustless, transparent, and interoperable energy exchange platform with transaction tokens that enable retailers to perform simple power transactions with one another and receive payments in real time from automated settlement systems(Cali & Fifield, 2019). In blockchain-based energy trading scheme, the consumers can choose the suppliers by their own preferences, i.e., trading with neighboring suppliers, or choosing clean energy, in order that the electricity bill could be reduced and the return on investment in distributed renewable energy could be increased.

The citizens can use the platform to observe the status of renewable energy production, while the producers ought to meet the capacity standard of 30 kWh if they need to join the platform to sell energy. Based on the survey of existing research work, this report firstly expounds the issues faced by energy transaction before and after the adoption of blockchain. Then, we analyze the relevant research on combining energy transaction with blockchain. Next, existing research are summarized and classified drawing on different aspects within the blockchain model. I summarize and highlight the problems and challenges that still need to be addressed in this field. The main contributions of this report can be summarized as mentioned below:

A comprehensive review of blockchain-based energy trading schemes is provided, and therefore the existing results are classified per the various challenges within the energy trading system used in this report.

Not only the theoretical research results, but also most appropriate blockchain-based energy trading applications are introduced and analyzed.

The existing blockchain-based energy trading schemes and applications are evaluated, and therefore the discussion of the potential future research directions also are given in this report.

Figure 1: Classification Diagram.

Section 2

2.1 Technology review

Over the last decade, the electric power sector has begun to change profoundly. And over that same time, block chain technology has emerged as powerful tool to manage complexity in a digital world. The confluence of the trends explains the surging investment in new ventures that apply block chain to energy.

2.1.1 Blockchain

In the 1.0 stage of block chain, it is actually a distributed ledger used as the underlying framework for Bitcoin(Kornmesser, 2008). As shown in Figure 2, the block chain is a chain structure composed of different blocks connected in series. Among them, each block is composed of a block header and a block body. In block body, the transaction data of a period of time are recorded. In block header, the main three parts are Prehash, Nonce, and Root hash. Root hash is the hash result of the transaction data and the digital signature of the miner, and the hash value of the previous block. Prehash, the hash value of the previous block, is used to build the links between the blocks. When a new block is generated, it is connected to the block chain by recording the Prehash. Meanwhile, all nodes will update synchronously to get a complete backup of the entire block chain. The consensus mechanism used in blockchain1.0 is Proof-Of-Work (POW). When new transactions are generated and broad casted, each node (miner) collects the new transactions into a block. All nodes (miners) try to find Nonce, the answer of one specific cryptographic puzzle. The miner who finds Nonce first will get billing right to broadcast the block to all other nodes. Other nodes check if Nonce found by the winner satisfies the cryptographic puzzle. Although the process of obtaining the answer is very difficult and requires a lot of computational effort, proving its correctness is very simple. If the new block is adopted, it will be added into the block chain. Block chain 2.0 adds smart contracts to the previous version and enables the migration from the currency market to other markets, allowing people to see the possibility of applying the advantages of block chain to other fields(Contracts & Society, 2015). Generally, the concept of block chain 2.0 includes the smart contract, digital assets, and financial applications. Differentfromblockchain1.0, blockchain2.0 is a decentralized market that provides a wider range of application scenarios for the financial section. The key idea is to use the distributed ledger of block chain to record, confirm and transfer various forms of contracts and properties. A smart contract is a computer protocol designed to disseminate, verify, or execute a contract in an informational manner. Smart contracts allow for trusted transactions without a third party, which are traceable and irreversible. In block chain 2.0, a smart contract is an application that is defined and implemented as code, which is automatically executed according to the pre-defined rules. The key characteristics of a smart contract are Autonomy, Self-sufficiency, and Decentralization: Autonomy means that, when the smart contract is launched and running, it no longer needs to make further contact with the initiating agent. Self-sufficiency means it can raise money by providing services and use that money to buy the resources it needs. Decentralization means that it is structurally distributed across network nodes.

Figure 2. Illustration of Blockchain 1.0.

According to the different needs of practical applications, the blockchain technology has gradually evolved into three application modes: the public blockchain, the consortium blockchain and the private blockchain. Public blockchain is a completely decentralized blockchain, private blockchain is a completely centralized blockchain, and the degree of decentralization of consortium blockchain is between the two. Consortium blockchain is applicable to an alliance of multiple entities, and the consensus process is only completed by some specific nodes. Private blockchain, on the other hand, is more suitable to be for data management within an organization. Hence, it may not require incentives mechanism. The idea of blockchain 3.0 is that you can think of every system in your life as somehow economic. Then, blockchain technology can be applied to any other field, supporting the possibility of reconfiguration in almost all fields involved by human beings. Due to the decentralized nature of blockchain, it can more fairly realize issues related to freedom, jurisdiction and review. It will help achieve global management across international boundaries, such as Name coin, which can break Internet censorship. Currently, blockchain 3.0 has been developed from a theoretical model to concrete applications. Enterprise Operation System (EOS)(Naiyu Wang et al., 2019), which introduces a new blockchain architecture to support vertical and horizontal extensions of distributed applications, is similar to the architecture of operating systems. It can provide multiple application scheduling. It supports millions of transactions per second, with no cost to the user.

2.1.2 Blockchain-Based Energy Trading

Currently, the application of blockchain in the field of energy trading has achieved significant success. One of the most common forms is based on P2P transactions, using the blockchain as the system framework. P2P networks can be roughly divided into two organizational modes, structured and unstructured. Each structured peer is built from a distributed hash table, and message routing is efficient but requires maintenance. The unstructured peer location is random, without the need for a centralized node search, but the query may not have a result. Evaluated both the

structured and unstructured P2P protocols to help planners better organize their networks. The conclusion is that both are highly scalable while the structured P2P protocols are more reliable by comparison. As shown in Figure 3, this report classifies the existing research results according to the various challenges in the energy trading system. First, the challenges mentioned in Section 3 can be divided into three parts: those encountered in the whole energy trading process, those encountered in the process of node consensus, and those encountered in the process of system optimization. For the first part, energy transaction, we divide it into three sub-parts: pre-transaction communication, buyer–seller matching, and transaction settlement. For example, “pre-trade communication” mainly focuses on how to achieve privacy protection in interactions under the condition of blockchain ledger disclosure. Pylon network, a successful practical project in Spain, is implemented with full data privacy protection(Cadre, Jacquot, Wan, & Alasseur, 2019).

Figure 3. Classification of Blockchain-based Energy Trading.

2.1.3 Energy and Smart Grids

The transition towards renewable energy sources is ongoing. In practice, this also leads to the fact that the production of energy will be more weather dependent and price variation is increasing. This kind of energy production is more unpredictable and fragmentary and requires more alternatives relating to balancing consumption and supply in both the short- and long term. Due to several local renewable energy sources, energy systems become more decentralized. All these facts require that the energy system should be more flexible in production and consumption. Also new energy storing solutions are needed.

Figure 4: 5G network slice brokering case diagram

In the future, there will be timely variance in the availability of energy. The balance of electricity production and consumption must be ensured somehow and flexibility in all energy resources is essential. One possibility is that electricity could be allocated autonomously by IoT entities among themselves. This could happen without the external intermediary's control (Bagdadee & Zhang, 2019).

The use case brokering for the energy industry has been presented (Brandon et al., 2016), where the internal electricity allocation in a housing society consists of various independent energy transactions between individual smart devices within the housing society as depicted in Fig.5.

In summation : A housing society's smart solar panel array starts to generate electricity. The solar panel array connects to a distributed block chain-based P2P marketplace. The marketplace's order book will be searched by the system to find out the highest bid for electricity. The array accepts the best available bid if it fulfills the requirements relating to its costs, investments and other possible parameters. If the bid is not fulfilling these predefined requirements, a new sell order would be issued.

Figure 5: Internal electrical allocation in a housing society, adapted from (Brandon et al., 2016).

A battery unit acts as an autonomous buffer for the energy marketplace. The battery unit analyses the marketplace's order book and history of market transactions for demand and supply trends, and electricity market price. According to these analyses, the next possible battery-related action will be decided: Recharge (purchase electricity), sell remaining energy or just wait for a better market situation. For example, if some device needs electricity it connects to the distributed marketplace and searches open sell orders from the order book. The device can, e.g., issue a new purchase order with a little higher bidding price than between the solar array and there charging battery. Then recharging of the battery can be terminated and the solar panel could start to feed the device at a higher price (Brandon et al., 2016).

During energy consumption peak hours, energy buffers might run low. In these situations, the energy can be purchased, for example, from the electric vehicles parked in the housing society's charging stations. The vehicle can decide to sell energy from its batteries for a good price, if it is estimated that the vehicle will not be used that day anymore. The vehicle can then buy the electricity, for example, during non-peak hours like at night and recharge itself for a lower price. In this kind of use case, some capabilities are required from the devices in the network. The devices need to be able to run a smart contract application client to combine the distributed market data with measurements of the traded electricity. In practice, basic computational functionality and networking abilities are required from the devices. The use case would also require a network that consists of full nodes. The smart devices could send and receive data by utilizing the network of full nodes. The network could be maintained, e.g. by housing societies, other buildings, and similar entities.

Section 3

3.1 Approaches to implementation

In order to prioritize among a broad range of use cases, an evaluation approach is needed for the assessment process that targets both the feasibility and suitability of each use case. The evaluation approach consists of three consecutive steps: the inventory of blockchain-based use cases, the assessment of the use case clusters and the prioritization among them based on their maturity level. This approach was developed throughout the process of collecting data in the first part of the study. It is accordingly built on the findings from the literature review and also from insights gained from the interviews and discussions held with both blockchain and energy experts. This approach will evaluate the use case clusters based on their ability to leverage the strengths of the blockchain technology, their strategy alignment with Vattenfall as well as their overall maturity level. The different stages of the framework are illustrated in Figure 6 below. In the following section, each of the three steps will be explained in greater detail.

Figure 6: the three consecutive steps and corresponding activities of the use case evaluation.

3.1.1 Inventory. In order to evaluate the use cases available on the market, a sample needs to be collected and mapped. The initial stage of the evaluation approach thus consists of an inventory stage where blockchain based energy use cases are collected, mapped and clustered based on their overall theme or target market. No evaluation or filtering is done at this stage, as all the use cases with a

connection to the energy sector were added to a long list and grouped into clusters. This stage thus consists of the following sub activities:

1. The collection of use cases in a long list of use cases
2. The clustering of use cases based on similarities in their overall objective
3. The mapping of the clusters in a:
 - a. Network map
 - b. Heat map

3.1.2 Assessment.

The assessment stage consists of the evaluation of the pre-selected use case clusters. A two-stage assessment approach is applied in order to reduce the number of clusters and narrow the scope of evaluation. On the first stage, all of the use case clusters are evaluated based on their fit with the business operations of an electric utility. By placing the clusters into the electricity value chain, the use cases deemed not to fit into the current or possible future, processes of an electric utility were removed from further analysis. As no prior screening of the clusters had been completed, this is an important step given the selected scope and delimitations. In the second stage, the remaining clusters were further assessed based on two criteria; their blockchain relevance and strategy alignment with Vattenfall.

The second stage of the framework thus consists of the following activities:

1. An initial evaluation based on the electricity value chain fit
2. A secondary evaluation based on:
 - a. Blockchain relevance
 - b. Strategy alignment with Vattenfall

3.1.3 Prioritization.

The final stage of the evaluation framework consists of a more thorough assessment of the remaining use case clusters to evaluate their maturity level. This is done in order to explore the factors that are currently stalling the development as well as to assess which clusters are deemed to be the closest to implementation at a larger scale. A maturity level framework based on four different dimensions was accordingly created; 1) Market Readiness Level, 2) Customer Readiness Level, 3) Technological Readiness Level, and 4) Regulations Readiness Level. The stages for these dimensions are measured from 1-4, where 1 is least mature, and 4 is the most mature stage. In the following section, each maturity dimension will be described together with a description of the respective steps. For the Market Readiness and Technological Readiness, additional level description is provided.

Market Readiness measures the maturity of energy utilities and how far businesses have come to incorporate the use case cluster into their business models. The levels stretch over four business process oriented phases; from ideation to scaling business to a sustainable and resilient commercial operation(Julien,2014).

Dimensions	MRL	Level Description	Stage
MRL	9	Business Model Defined Coherently	4
	8	Product/Service defined	
CRL	7	Value Proposition defined	3
	6	Competitors analysis and positioning	
TRL	5	Industry analysis with respect to social and environmental impact	2
	4	Target defined	
RRL	3	Market research	1
	2	System analysis and impact	
	1	Unsatisfied needs have been identified, identification of business	

Figure 7: The Market readiness levels

Section 4

4.1 Discussion of key challenges and future out look

The blockchain projects and research initiatives reviewed in this report show that block chains are a promising technology for a wide area of services and use cases in the energy sector. The large number of established energy companies and utilities that are currently involved in DLT projects, as well as the investor interest in this area, clearly shows the potential value of this emerging technology for the energy industry. The real, long-term value is, however, yet to be proven, specially as most initiatives have trialled the technology in relatively small-scale projects that are still in an early development phase. As a result, several questions will need to be answered before mainstream adoption of the blockchains in the energy industry. First and for most, blockchain technologies need to prove they can offer the scalability, speed and security required for the proposed use cases. Research efforts on distributed consensus algorithms, which are crucial to achieving these objectives, are still ongoing, however a solution that combines all desired characteristics cannot yet be achieved without significant trade-offs. PoW algorithms are more mature and secure, but on the other hand are also slow and very energy intensive. As a result, blockchain developers are increasingly moving towards PoS schemes that are energy efficient, faster and more scalable. Other promising solutions include techniques such as 'sharding' that enable parallel processing. Often these solutions may come, however, to the expense of security and decentralisation. Early adopters of blockchain technologies face the challenge of selecting the right consensus mechanism and system architecture, without having a clear long-term picture of the advantages and downsides that each approach has to offer.

Hence, it is clear that blockchain technologies have already passed the proof of concept stage for several use cases but require further development to achieve desired operational and performance objectives. Several recent developments, such as the Energy Web blockchain, can be scaled up to thousands of transactions per second. Similar future developments will significantly determine blockchain adoption in several applications, such as for IoT platforms and services that require very fast confirmation and large numbers of transactions. Resilience to security risks stemming from unintentionally bad system design or malicious attacks are highly likely. Blockchains face additional risks such as possible malfunctions at early stages of development due to lack of experience with large-scale applications. Blockchain ecosystems rely heavily on coding new algorithms, a procedure that can be prone to errors. Security breaches are still highly likely before the technology becomes mature, which could result in bad publicity and delays in acceptance from consumers. With respect to cyber-attacks, Bitcoin, the oldest blockchain implementation, has proved to be relatively resilient, but other platforms such as Ethereum, have been the target of serious attacks in the past. Crucially, vulnerabilities in terms of cyber-

security often come from peripheral applications, such as digital wallets or smart contracts. Resilience to such attacks is of great importance, especially for applications in critical infrastructure, such as energy systems. Another important challenge is that blockchain systems have currently high development costs. Blockchains may realise significant cost savings by circumventing intermediaries, however for several use cases, they might not have the competitive advantage against already existing solutions in well-established markets. For example, energy transactions can be recorded in conventional databases, such as relational databases that are designed to recognise relations between stored items of information (Hertz-Shargel & Livingston, 2019). These solutions are already largely available and currently faster and less costly to operate, albeit they cannot offer immutability of records or transparency. Blockchain systems may require costly new infrastructure, such as custom ICT equipment and software, the costs of which need to be outweighed by benefits achieved by data integrity, enhanced security and elimination of the need for a trusted intermediary. In the energy sector, smart meters are currently being rolled out without significant computational capabilities, hence integrating the existing smart metering and grid infrastructure with distributed ledgers could come with significant costs. At present, information in blockchain systems can be transferred for very low costs, but validation and verification of data comes with high hardware and energy costs (Clinch, 2000). Proof of stake or proof of authority algorithms may significantly improve this in the future. In the field of grid communications however, blockchain systems would need to compete with already established solutions such as telemetry, which is not only more mature, but also significantly cheaper technology solution. Adding to the cost of information verification, blockchain systems also face an additional cost of storing the data in continuously expanding ledgers. Promising solutions proposed to address this challenge is storing actual data in 'side chains' and operating the blockchain as a control layer rather than as a storage layer.

Section 5

5.1 Conclusion

This report summarized the existing literature on blockchain-based energy trading markets. It presents research on many relevant issues, from the removal of the centralized control and the transition to a distributed architecture, the security and privacy issues, transaction object matching issues, the auction pricing mechanism at the time of settlement, to the cost minimization and benefit maximization of the system. In an age where possible pandemics of world scale may become common, the more efficient and effective digital transaction technologies will be much needed in keeping supply and demand going. Finally, the report highlighted the unsolved problems and provided insights for future directions. Increasingly more experiments show that the distributed system architecture employed by blockchain can bring greater flexibility and better performance to the energy trading market. The development of blockchain-based energy trading has made some progress and is gradually maturing. In general, the most common application form of blockchain technology in energy trading is the main framework of the system, which plays an important role in storing transaction data and ensuring security. Meanwhile, there are also those who use blockchain only as an implementation tool to achieve certain functions. Furthermore, this report highlights that more and more blockchain products have solved the intrinsic “problems of blockchain” (e.g., IOTA). Different types of blockchain can also be combined to achieve the improvement of system performance with their own advantages, for example, the combination of the consortium blockchain and the private blockchain. Besides, the blockchain products should also provide interfaces for customization.

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